
Kinetics of the adsorption of heavy metals by clay in the activated state

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Abstract Presence of heavy metals in the aquatic systems has become a serious problem. As a result, there has been a great deal of attention given to new technologies for removal of heavy metal from contaminated waters. Biosorption is one such emerging technology which utilized naturally occurring waste materials to sequester heavy metals from industrial wastewater.

In this study, we carried out the kinetics of élimination of cobalt, cadmium and manganese in solution by adsorption on clay treated by acid chloridric of the region maysour. In order to optimise the operating conditions of the adsorption process, various studies on the kinetics, capacity, weight, initial métal concentration and was conducted. The kinetics of biosorption process was well described by the pseudo 2nd order kinetics model. It was concluded that adsorbent prepared from clay to the activated state by chemical way using the acid chloride at moderate temperature of the region may sour be utilized for the treatment of heavy metals of cobalt, cadmium and manganese in wastewater.

The thermodynamic has allowed us to deduce of the negative value of ΔS° that it is a decrease in the disorder on the interface solid/solute solution system during the adsorption process.

Keywords Adsorption, clay, heavy metals, activation, kinetics modeling

Introduction

Heavy metals are toxic to aquatic flora and fauna even in relatively low concentrations. Some metals can be assimilated, stored and concentrated by organisms [1].

Removing metals from wastewater requires development of new sorbents. A wide range of commercial sorbents including chelating resins and activated carbon are available for metal sorption, but they are relatively expensive. In recent years, numerous low cost natural materials have been proposed as potential biosorbents.

These include moss peat [2], algae [3], leaf mould [4], sea weeds [5], coconut husk [6], sago waste [7], peanut hull [8], hazelnut [9], bagasse [10], rice hull [11], sugar beet pulp [12], plants biomass and bituminous coal [13]. In this research adsorbent are prepared from the clay treated by hydrochloric acid to analyse its behaviour towards heavy metals Co, Cd, Mn in solution. The effect of some operating conditions like temperature, and initial concentration of

metal Co, Cd, Mn biosorption were studied. In order to evaluate its respective adsorption capacity and to define the optimum conditions for maximum adsorption. Parameters, kinetics and thermodynamics are analyzed.

Theoretical Part

Optimization of heavy metals biosorption

Optimization of the influencing parameters is an essential step in the solid-liquid extraction processes; on one hand it allows us to study the sorption kinetics on the other hand to determine the maximum concentration adsorbed by the solid in the selected operating conditions.

Kinetic studies of adsorption of Co, Cd and Mn ions on clay

The evolution of the kinetics of fixing metal ions on clays or on hydroxides attest above all the reversibility of the exchanges put in play the physical nature of the adsorbent-metal interactions. Thus, after contacting the metal solution with the material and during a well-defined agitation time, we proceed to filtration using a syringe filter with a porosity of 0.45 μm and then analysis of our Samples by atomic absorption spectroscopy.

Modeling the kinetics (article de chrom)

Knowledge of the adsorption kinetics is of considerable practical interest for the optimal use of an adsorbent in an operation based on adsorption phenomena. The literature reports several kinetic models [14-17] but a large majority is traditionally based on first order or second order reaction schemes with respect to the amount of solute fixed. To determine order of the adsorption kinetics, we have adopted the following kinetic models:

- first-order kinetic models
- second-order kinetic models
- Elovitch models
- diffusion intra particule models

To fit the experimental metal removal data and to assist water treatment process design.

a) First order model

The model of the first order is generally expressed by [18]:

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = K_L (q_e - q_t) \quad (1)$$

Which carry out, after integration, to [19]:

$$\ln(q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - K_L t \quad (2)$$

b) Second order model

It is an equation which is often employed on the representation of kinetics of adsorption. It is presented in the form [20]:

$$\frac{dq_t}{dt} = K_b (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (3)$$

The integration of the equation (14) permits to obtaining the equation [21]:

$$\frac{1}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_b \cdot q_e^2} \cdot \frac{1}{t} + \left(\frac{1}{q_e} \right) \quad (4)$$

This presents the linearization of the second class equation; It is the equation which helps us to extract the parameters of the second.

When tracing $\frac{t}{q} = f(t)$, we find a line of slope $\frac{1}{q_e}$ et d'ordonnée à l'origine $\frac{1}{K_b \cdot q_e^2}$

c) Elovitch models

The Elovitch equation is one of the most used models: satisfactory in chemical adsorption processes and is suitable for systems with heterogeneous adsorbent surfaces. It is given as follows [22]:

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = \alpha e^{-\beta \cdot q \cdot t} \quad (5)$$

Or :

α : The adsorbed initial velocity (mg / g.min).

β : The adsorption constant (g / mg).

To simplify the Elovitch equation, it is assumed that $\alpha \cdot \beta \cdot t \gg 1$ and $q = 0$ to $t = 0$ (the limit condition), this equation becomes:

$$q(t) = \beta \ln(\alpha \beta) + \beta \ln t \quad (6)$$

When we trace $q = f(\ln t)$, we find a straight line of slope β and of ordered at the origin β

$\ln(\alpha\beta)$

d) Diffusion intra particle models

The model of intra particle diffusion is proposed by Weber and Morris. According to this model, the adsorption process can be characterized by four steps:

- 1) Transfer of the solute to the boundary layer surrounding the particle.
- 2) Transfer of the solute from the boundary layer to the adsorbent surface
- 3) The transfer of the solute to the adsorbent sites: diffusion in micro and macro pores.
- 4) Interaction between the molecules of the solute and the active sites of the surface: adsorption, complexation and precipitation.

The first two steps are generally rapid because the stirring of the solution will eliminate the gradients of the concentration which can be established in the vicinity of the particle: the intra-particle diffusion then becomes the limiting step. This model is represented by the following equation III:

$$q(t) = K \cdot \sqrt{t} + C \quad (7)$$

with:

K: Intra-particle diffusion constant (mg / g min).

The constant k is deduced from the slope of the linear part of the equation representing this model. When we trace $q(t) = f(\sqrt{t})$, we find a line of slope K and of ordinate at the origin C.

Determination of thermodynamic parameters

The thermodynamic properties of a system are statistical means corresponding to a large number of molecules. The energy of a solute molecule varies when it approaches the surface to reach a minimum at a certain distance, near an adsorption site. This minimum is called a potential energy well or, more simply, a potential well characterized by (23):

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (8)$$

It is the Gibbs adsorption energy, which is composed of two terms: an enthalpic term which expresses the energies of interactions between the molecules and the adsorbent surface, and an entropic term which expresses the modification and arrangement of Molecules in the liquid phase and on the surface. The relative importance of the two terms depends on the adsorbate-adsorbent system envisaged.

The calculation of certain thermodynamic parameters is indispensable in determining the nature of the retention process. From the equilibrium constant K_c , which can be calculated by the following relation [23, 24]:

$$K_c = \frac{q_e}{c_e}$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = -R \cdot T \cdot \ln K_c \quad (9)$$

$$\ln(k_c) = \frac{\Delta G}{R} - \frac{\Delta H}{R \cdot T} \quad (10)$$

With

K_c : Balance constant

ΔG° : The free enthalpy (joule / mole)

ΔH° : The enthalpy (joule / mole)

ΔS° : The entropy (joule / mole.K)

T: Absolute temperature (K)

Qe: equilibrium adsorption capacity (mg / g)

This: Equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate

R: Perfect gas constant (8.314 Joule / mole K)

The adsorption heats ΔH° and the ΔS° entropies of the metal ions on the clay matrix are determined graphically by plotting $\ln K_c$ as a function of the inverse of the temperature of the medium in degree kelvin.

Results and Discussion

Determination of optimum adsorption conditions

A- Effect of the initial concentration of adsorbate

The application of the process for removing metal ions by clay from may to a boulomane region on synthetic solutions at different concentrations [10, 20, 30, 40, 50 mg / l] in a volume of 100 ml and under the optimum stirring time conditions already mentioned, allows us to study the kinetics of adsorption of each metal. (See yield evolution and determine the maximum adsorbed amount at equilibrium).

Figs. 1, 2 and 3 represent respectively the values of the adsorption histogram yields realized for the three metals. We find that the concentration value fixed in Mn by the adsorbent at equilibrium is greater for the initial solutions of concentration 30 mg / l. The results of the tests carried out also show that the yield is variable and presents values that are quite high, which makes it possible to say that the Mn exhibits a significant affinity vis the clay. The largest calculated values are of the order of 85.25% (Figure 1). This suggests that this material has a high adsorption capacity at medium concentrations The results obtained (Figures 2 and 3) show that the removal efficiency of Cd and Co varies with the dose of the adsorbate: a maximum efficiency after 20 minutes is obtained which is 99.95 % for A dose of 10 mg / l in Cd and 95.87 % for the same dose in Co.

We can see that the yields decrease gradually with the increase of the initial content of Cobalt and Cadmium. In the copper concentration range between 6.3 and 31.7 mg / l, the authors [25] showed that the effectiveness of binding of copper to goethite decreases. This result was accompanied by the decrease of the pH relative to the initial pH, associated with a release of H^+ protons during several fixing operations. These same authors, this decrease is related to a process of substitution between the protons of goethite and the Cu^{2+} cations according to a simplified scheme, a scheme that can be applicable for the Cobalt, Cadmium and Manganese ions:

In the experiments we carried out, we also observed a slight decrease (Table 1) in pH from the initial pH with an increase in the initial content of the three metal ions.

Figure 1: Yield as a function of the initial concentration in Mn Optimal parameters:
 $pH = 6.5 - \phi \leq 6 \mu m$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm $T = 20^\circ C$ - C (clay) = 0.2 g / l

Figure 2: Yield according to the initial concentration in Co Optimal parameters: pH = 6.5 - $\phi \leq 63 \mu\text{m}$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm T = 20 ° C - C (clay) = 0.2 g / l

Figure 3: Yield as a function of the initial Cd concentration Optimal parameters: pH = 6.5 - $\phi \leq 63 \mu\text{m}$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm T = 20 ° C - C (clay) = 0.2 g / l

Table 1: Evolution of the removal efficiency of metal ions Co, Cd and Mn (R (%)) and pH End of treatment for varying initial Co, Cd and Mn concentrations

Metallic ions Concentration (mg/l)	Cobalt		manganese		Cadmium	
	R%	pH	R%	pH	R%	pH
10	95.87	6.3	69.5	6.25	99.95	6.25
20	92.5	6.3	83.79	6.15	84.43	6.1
30	91.7	6.1	85.26	6.11	64.61	6.05
40	80.67	6.05	77.56	5.85	51.61	6
50	78.31	5.9	66.3	5.7	50.8	5.8

B- Effect of temperature

The temperature of the medium is a very important parameter in the adsorption process, as it exerts a considerable influence on the sorption rate [26].

Some authors have shown, however, that increasing the temperature of the medium tends to decrease the adsorption capacity of the metal [27,28]. However, other authors have shown that the adsorption capacity increases with increasing temperature [29, 30, 31]. In general, in most species, the toxicity of metals varies in the same direction as temperature [32]. However, some authors have shown that the toxicity of metals decreases with increasing temperature [33].

In our case the results of our tests are compatible with the first hypothesis. The temperatures used in this experimental phase vary from 20 to 45 °C. The choice of this temperature range makes it possible to avoid the significant evaporation of the solution which could have explained the increase in the adsorption observed for the metal ions. According to figures (4, 5 and 6), the temperature acts directly on this process, and the fixing is maximum at 20 °C. The exploitation of the histograms of figures 4, 5 and 6 shows that cadmium shows an important affinity for adsorbing on the clay material vis-a-vis the other two ions its adsorption density is equal to (99.95%). This value has the highest value under the same optimal conditions.

The kinetic study also shows that the sorption decreases by increasing the temperature Figures 7,8 and 9). This explains why the adsorption of these metal ions in an aqueous medium by the clay is exothermic at a temperature of 20 °C. The values of the residual concentration of Mn, Co and Cd for this medium after 20 minutes of stirring are

respectively: 3.051; 0.412 and 0.005 mg / l. From Figure 7, the residual Mn concentrations approach within 15 minutes. A dissimilarity was observed during equilibrium, a deflection of the pace representing the temperature 20 ° C with respect to the other two paces. , However the fastening capacity is important at low temperatures. As shown in Figure 8, the change in residual concentrations at equilibrium is very significant. However, the equilibrium concentration is further reduced from 7.7212 to 0.4128 mg / l respectively for the temperatures 45 and 20 ° C. Therefore, adsorption is favorable at low and unfavorable temperatures for high temperatures. This is proved by a thermodynamic study which will be discussed later.

9 shows that the effect of temperature on the adsorption capacity of the Cd ions on the clay is not very significant. In this temperature range, a slight decrease in the adsorption capacity is observed when the temperature increases from 20 ° C. to 45 ° C.

Figure 4: Yield of adsorption of cadmium as a function of temperature

Figure 5: Yield of adsorption of manganese as a function of temperature

Figure 6: Cobalt adsorption efficiency as a function of temperature

Figure 7: followed by the residual concentration as a function of time

Figure 8: followed by the residual concentration as a function of time

Figure 9: followed by the residual concentration as a function of time

Kinetic studies of the adsorption of Co, Cd and Mn ions on clay

From figures 10, 11 and 12, examination of the results obtained makes it possible to deduce that the kinetics of fixing the metal ions on the clay support is very rapid. The equilibrium time can be estimated at 20 minutes of agitation whatever the type and the adsorbate doses.

This time corresponds to the maximum efficiency of the adsorption of the metal ions and therefore to the minimum of the residual metal ion contents. Beyond this interval, we can nevertheless observe that the residual concentration of these cations remains unchanged. Similar behaviour has been observed from several authors:

- Benjamin et al (1), by studying the adsorption of copper on iron oxide surfaces, showed that the adsorption kinetics were rapid and reached equilibrium after 20 minutes.
- the work of (34) found that the equilibrium time was 20 min during a kinetic study of Mn adsorption on a purified kaolin matrix.
- A study on activated carbon reported that it rapidly fixes a maximum amount of Cu and Zn ions within a few minutes to stabilize their concentrations in the solution [35].
- the removal of cadmium by adsorption on sodium and calcium bentonites was studied by [36]. The result of this study makes it possible to deduce that the kinetics of fixation of Cadmium on bentonites is very prompt. The equilibrium time can be estimated at 20 minutes of agitation. Moreover, the difference between the adsorption kinetics according to the initial concentration in each metal is not significant, but a near equilibrium is reached quickly.

Our results could be explained by the mechanisms of adsorption. These mechanisms take place in two phases:

A rapid, short-lived adsorption phase during which the abatement of the pollutant charge is high.

-A phase of slow adsorption, of a longer duration when the reduction of the solute is low. This is often explained by the fact that the migration of the molecules along the macropores is easy and therefore allows an important adsorption, whereas the diffusion in the micropores is made more difficult.

The interactions that allow this phase change are of two kinds:

- The physical adsorption (physisorption) involves only Van Der Waals forces (ΔH of -20 to -40 kJ / mol), the interactions are reversible and the process is essentially a diffusion phenomenon in the pores of materials.
- Chemical adsorption (chemisorption), an established chemical bond between molecule-solute and functional groups in the surface. Chemisorption is distinguished from physisorption by higher binding energies (ΔH of -80 to -200 kJ / mol) and by irreversible adsorption fixation at very specific adsorption sites.

Figure 10: Monitoring the residual concentration of manganese Optimum parameters $\phi \leq 63 \mu\text{m}$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ - $C(\text{clay}) = 0.2 \text{ g/l}$

Figure 11: Monitoring the residual Cobalt concentration Optimal parameters: $\text{pH} = 6.5$ - $\phi \leq 63 \mu\text{m}$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm $T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ - $C(\text{clay}) = 0.2 \text{ g/l}$

Figure 12: Monitoring the residual cadmium concentration Optimal parameters: $pH = 6.5 - \phi \leq 63 \mu m$ - Stirring speed = 400 rpm $T = 20^\circ C$ - C (clay) = 0.2 g / l

Kinetic Models

The application of kinetic model equations to our experimental data allowed us to plot the lines presented in Figures (13; 14; 15; 16 and 17) and to calculate the kinetic parameter values (Table 2 and 3).

Discussion

From the linear regression of the preceding tests, it can be observed that graphically, the experimental data approximate the empirical data at the level of the kinetic model of the pseudo second order more than those of the kinetic model of the pseudo first order. This is valid for the two inorganic pollutants Cd and Mn, with differences in the chosen concentrations: For Cd, the model is reliable with the concentration range (10, 20 and 30 mg / l), whereas Mn does not Shows a degree of proximity to this model compared to a single concentration of 20 mg / l. (The correlation factors of the first pseudo-order model do not give reasonable values). Another observation is worth noting: following our analysis of the correlation factors, we also note that the adsorbed capacities found experimentally merge closely with those calculated theoretically.

Similar results have been reported on the adsorption of green-gloss on clay-based adsorbents [37-40] and on various adsorbents [41-43], and adsorption of Methylene blue on different adsorbents. [44-47].

Nevertheless, we find that the regression for the pseudo first order model is close to 90%, and this for an initial concentration of 10 mg / l in Co ion. On the other hand, the deviations between the theoretically and experimentally adsorbed maximum capacities (Δq_e) are minimal with a variation factor of 15% for the Lagergren model (Table 3). Therefore, we can conclude that the kinetics of sorption of the Cobalt by the clay in aqueous medium follows a kinetics of the pseudo first order.

Furthermore, Weber et al. [48] reported that if intra particle diffusion is involved in the sorption process, by increasing the adsorbed amount as a function of the square root of time, we obtain a straight line. This step is limiting if the line passes through the origin. In the case where these lines do not pass through the origin, this indicates that the diffusion in the pores is not the only mechanism limiting the sorption kinetics. It appears that other mechanisms are involved [48-49]. The slope k is defined as a velocity parameter which characterizes the adsorption kinetics in the region where diffusion into the pores is the limiting step.

On the other hand, the ordinate at the origin indicates the effect of the boundary layer, the latter is large and the contribution to external diffusion in the sorption rate limitation is independent [50-51].

In our case, we note that the set of straight lines resulting from the function $q_e = f(t^{1/2})$ do not pass through the origin, which shows that the diffusion of the metal ions into the pores is not the only mechanism limiting sorption kinetics (Figure 13, 14 and 15). The parameters of Weber et al and the correlation coefficients are presented in Table (3). The adsorption rates of the metal ions are very low for the adsorbent studied. The values of C increase with the increase in the concentration of the metal ions indicating the increase in the thickness of the boundary layer and the decrease in the possibility of the external mass transfer [52]. The phenomenon of diffusion exists and operates simultaneously with the processes of adsorption which are the pseudo-second-order and the pseudo-first-order.

The trace of the straight lines from the adsorbed quantity as a function of the logarithm of time $q = f(\ln t)$ has allowed us to conclude that the external transport established by the Elovitch model seems to be a step controlling the speed of the overall sorption process. Cd in aqueous solution by the clay (Figure14).

This phenomenon is justified by the results of the tests carried out, where we find that the correlation coefficients for the three solutions chosen and under the optimum operating conditions are of the order of 0.90 and more (Table 3).

Figure13: Modeling of the adsorption kinetics of the Co, Mn and Cd ions on the clay in function of the initial concentration for the pseudo-first-order model

Figure 14: Application of the Blanchard model to the sorption of metal ions (Co, Mn and Cd)

Table 2: Results of models of adsorption kinetics of metal ions as a function of concentration: Pseudo first order and Pseudo second order

	Concentration (mg/l)	Pseudo-seconde-ordre				Pseudo-premier-ordre					
		Kb (g/mg.min)	Qe thé (mg/g)	Qe exp (mg/g)	ΔQ_e /	R^2	K_{La} (min^{-1})	Qe thé (mg/g)	Qe exp (mg/g)	ΔQ_e /	R^2
Co	10	0.17	1.273	4.793	73	0.88	0.114	4.035	4.793	15	0.836
	20	0.126	3.378	9.26	63	0.97	0.051	2.69	9.26	70	0.932
	30	9,8.10 ⁻²	5.71	13.68	58	0.98	0.038	3.38	13.68	75	0.916
Mn	10	0.293	5.18	3.97	30	0.99	0.023	1.624	3.47	53	0.751
	20	5.35.10 ⁻²	9.70	8.37	15	0.941	0.026	2.611	8.37	68	0.980
	30	6.31.10 ⁻²	4.67	12.79	65	0.93	0.149	7.007	12.79	45	0.843
Cd	10	8.76	0.042	4.97	99	0.99	0.359	0.13	4.975	97	0.931
	20	0.125	10.309	8.44	22	0.99	0.012	3.83	8.445	54	0.974
	30	0.16	9.17	9.7	5	0.99	0.152	1.692	9.741	82	0.843

Figure (15): Application of the Blanchard model to the sorption of metal ions (Co, Mn and Cd)

Figure 16: Modeling the adsorption kinetics of Cd on activated clay of the concentration for the Elovitch models and initial intra-particle scattering

Figure 17: Modeling of Mn adsorption kinetics on activated clay as a function of concentration for Elovitch models and initial intra-particle scattering

Table 3: Results of models of kinetics of adsorption of metal ions: Elovitch model and intra particle diffusion model

	Elovitch				Diffusion intra particule		
	Concentrati on initiale (mg/l)	α (mg/g.min).	β (g/mg).	R^2	K (mg/g min ^{-1/2}).	C (mg/g)	R^2
Co	10	1.88	1.13	0.765	0.795	0.892	0.825
	20	9,52.10 ³	0.69	0.878	0.480	6.128	0.922
	30	7,2.10 ⁵	0.737	0.847	0.513	9.758	0.896
Mn	10	400	0.309	0.867	0.203	1.545	0.813
	20	8,19.10 ⁴	0.496	0.999	0.334	5.326	0.99
	30	25	1.811	0.802	1.268	6.982	0.857
Cd	10	-	0.014	1	0.009	4.937	0.994
	20	10 ⁵	0.359	0.916	0.09	4.937	0.994
	30	10 ⁴	0.715	0.90	0.471	7.820	0.852

Determination of thermodynamic parameters

The adsorption heats ΔH° and the ΔS° entropies of the metal ions on the clay matrix are determined graphically by plotting $\ln Kc$ as a function of the inverse of the temperature of the medium in degree kelvin. The straight lines of the function $\ln kc = f(1/T)$ are shown in figure (18).

The results are confirmed by the work of P. Yadava and S. Tyagi [53]. Metal ions leave the solid phase as the temperature increases [54] and the solubility of the metal ions in the aqueous phase probably increases with the decrease in the resulting metal ion concentration in the solid phase. Excess energy stimulates desorption rather than adsorption [55]. The values of the thermodynamic constants deduced are summarized in Table 4.

According to table (4), the adsorption of the three metal ions by the clay is exothermic, translated by a negative value of ΔH and means that the system releases heat to the external environment. The low value of this heat for the Mn-clay couple implies that the adsorption of the metal ions is a non-specific adsorption for the clay surfaces and suggests the existence of a physical adsorption which involves weak attraction forces of types. Van Der Wals The limit value of ΔH found for the element Cd on the clay (50.989 kJ / mol) can be interpreted by a combination of chemisorption and physisorption.

The enthalpy of the Cobalt-clay system is important (141.50 kJ / mol). It reflects chemical adsorption, it is specific, it results in the establishment of a chemical bond between the solute molecule and the functional groups in the surface Clay.

Negative values of entropy suggest that no critical changes have occurred in the internal clay structure during the adsorption of these metal ions [55-56].

Moreover, they show that the adsorption of these metals on the clay studied is accompanied by a certain order. This result shows that the molecules of the metals adsorbed on the studied clay surface are organized with respect to the

situation in the aqueous phase. The free enthalpy value for the Cd-clay torque for the different temperatures is less than zero ($\Delta G < 0$), which proves that the elimination process is instantaneous [57-58]. The same remark has been given for The Co-Argile and Mn-Clay couples at a temperature of 20 °C. However, reactions for which $\Delta G > 0$ will be non-spontaneous reactions. Indeed, for the Mn-clay or Co-clay pairs, the values of ΔG are positive or beyond a temperature of 20 °C. These reactions are thus considered as endergonics, the implementation of which will require an energy coupling with a second reaction provided that the sum of the two free enthalpy variations is negative.

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